

Isolation and purification of phenanthrene from phenanthrene waste I

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Abstract : Isolation and purification of phenanthrene from phenanthrene waste has been studied by fractionation, recrystallization and precipitation. GC apparatus was used to investigate the purity of phenanthrene. Experimental results showed that the purity of phenanthrene was increased from 50.29% to 90.32%. And commercial grade phenanthrene was obtained by purification, the melting point of the product was 96 ~ 98 °C, and the yield of phenanthrene 54.3%.

Keywords : Phenanthrene waste, phenanthrene, purification.

Introduction

Next to naphthalene in terms of quantity, phenanthrene, at the concentration of 4~5%, is the most abundant constituent in coal tar. Phenanthrene can be oxidized to 9,10-phenanthrenequinone and 2,2'-diphenic acid. It can also be used to prepare anthracene¹. Electrically conductive substances, e.g. for use in batteries and solar cells, liquid crystal, used for optical-electronic applications and resins^{2,3}, such as a polyamide-polyimide resin⁴, which is suitable for use in high temperature insulators, printed circuit boards and laminators can be produced from phenanthrene. It can also be used as a plasticizer for plastics, molding compounds, stabilizers for mineral oil products, water reducing agents^{5,6} and so on.

Phenanthrene waste, which is a residue/by-product after isolation of anthracene and carbazole from crude anthracene, contains mainly phenanthrene (about 50 ± 5%), and a small quantity of fluorene, anthracene, carbazole, etc. These impurities are difficult to remove, thus very pure phenanthrene has been unavailable commercially. The present study describes the isolation and purification of phenanthrene from phenanthrene waste by fractionation, recrystallization and precipitation. Commercial grade phenanthrene was obtained by purification. This work had the advantages of simple procedure, repeated use of solvent and economy.

Experimental

Materials :

Phenanthrene waste was obtained from a local market. For recrystallization and precipitation, commercial grade chemicals were used.

Procedure :

The isolation and purification of phenanthrene was carried out by fractionation, recrystallization and precipitation, and the procedures (see Fig. 1) were as follows :

(i) Fractional distillation :

At first, phenanthrene waste was subjected to fractionation. The cut was distilled in the range of 310 to 350 degree Celsius wherein distilled phenanthrene was obtained.

(ii) Recrystallization :

The distillate fraction was dissolved in xylene. By recrystallization, impurities, such as anthracene, carbazole, etc. were recrystallized from dimethyl benzene, filtered and removed, whereas phenanthrene was in the mother liquor. By evaporating off xylene, a middle product of phenanthrene was obtained and the recovered solvent dimethyl benzene was repeated for use.

(iii) Precipitation :

Finally, *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) was employed as a solvent, and water precipitator. Phenanthrene was selectively precipitated with water from DMF and filtered to obtain commercial grade of phenanthrene. By evaporating off a portion of water, DMF was recovered for further use.

Fig. 1. Separation flow chart.

The melting point of the product was determined by a melting point apparatus (X-4, Beijing, China). The quantitative analysis of phenanthrene was performed by means of gas chromatography (Type : GC-2010, Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan). Chromatograph conditions are as follows:

Column : fused silica capillary column (column I.D. No. : US1355961H, J&W Scientific Incorporation, USA), liquid phase : DB-1 (100% dimethylpolysiloxane), film thickness : 0.25 μm , column dimensions : 30 m \times 0.254 mm, detector : FID, temperature : injector 310 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, column 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, detector 240 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, flow control mode : pressure, column inlet pressure : 100 kPa, split ratio : 50, carrier gas : N_2 , solvent : acetone.

Results and discussion

Phenanthrene waste : Phenanthrene waste contains mainly phenanthrene. From the waste chromatogram (see Fig. 2), the qualitative and quantitative analysis of phenanthrene waste was obtained by comparison of the standard and sample retention times and calculating area percent of chromatograph peak. The results are shown in Table 1. It indicates that in the waste main impurities are fluorene (14.81%), anthracene (7.87%) and carbazole (3.47%).

Fractional distillation : 100 g of phenanthrene waste was subjected to fractional distillation and 48 g of a phenan-

Table 1. Results of analysis of phenanthrene waste

Peak number	Components	Retention times	Percent composition
1	Phenanthrene	9.136	50.29%
2	Anthracene	9.387	7.87%
3	Carbazole	10.017	3.47%
4	Fluorene	5.518	14.81%
5	Acetone (solvent)	2.0	-

threne fraction boiling in the range 310~350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was obtained. The distillate fraction chromatogram is shown in Fig. 3 which shows low boiling substances, such as fluorene and high boiling substances, whose retention times are greater than 12 min, are basically removed and the purity of phenanthrene reaches to 70.82%.

Recrystallization : 10 g distillate fraction was used for recrystallization. Phenanthrene is easily soluble in xylene, whereas anthracene and carbazole are soluble in hot xylene, but insoluble in cold xylene. By using these properties, recrystallization was conducted. The chromatogram of the middle product is shown in Fig. 4. It shows that a great portion of anthracene, carbazole, etc. are removed.

Precipitation : Finally, the middle product just described was purified by water precipitation. A mixture of anthracene and phenanthrene can be separated one

Fig. 2. The waste chromatogram.

Fig. 3. The phenanthrene fraction chromatogram.

Fig. 4. The chromatogram of the middle product.

from the other by selective precipitation of the phenanthrene from DMF solution. Whereas any impurities, which accompany anthracene and phenanthrene mixture, will also be dissolved to a great extent in the DMF. However these impurities are not precipitated in detrimental quantities. Thus, the phenanthrene obtained is basically free of these impurities.

In the study, we investigated effects of the quantity of DMF employed, precipitation temperature and time on the purity and yields of phenanthrene. The results are shown in Tables 2~4 and Fig. 5. They show that when the amount of DMF employed is 50 ml, precipitation time 20 min, and precipitation temperature 50 °C, the purity and yields are greater. Therefore, under such conditions, water precipitation was conducted to obtain a commercial grade product, whose freezing point was 96~98 °C. The product chromatogram is shown in Fig. 6. It shows that impurities are basically removed.

Fig. 5. Effects of the amount of DMF employed.

Table 3. Effects of precipitation time

Run	DMF (ml)	Time (min)	Temp. (°C)	Purity (%)	Yields (%)
1	50	10	60	86.35	42.45
2	50	20	60	90.16	45.85
3	50	30	60	89.42	42.72
4	50	40	60	87.64	42.46

Table 2. Effects of the amount of DMF employed

Run	DMF (ml)	Time (min)	Temp. (°C)	Purity (%)	Yields (%)
1	30	20	50	85.74	40.4
2	40	20	50	85.64	48.3
3	50	20	50	90.32	54.3
4	60	20	50	89.23	45.5

Table 4. Effects of precipitation temperature

Run	DMF (ml)	Time (min)	Temp. (°C)	Purity (%)	Yields (%)
1	40	30	40	82.50	46.52
2	40	30	50	86.64	47.35
3	40	30	60	86.10	42.51
4	40	30	70	85.56	41.62

Fig. 6. The product chromatogram.

Conclusions :

(i) From phenanthrene waste, phenanthrene was refined by fractional distillation, recrystallization and water precipitation. The study showed that, by isolation and purification, the purity of phenanthrene was increased from 50.29 to 90.32%. Commercial grade phenanthrene was obtained (freezing point 96~98 °C) and the yield was 54.3%. This method had the advantages of simple operation, repeat use of solvent and economy and the study has been applied to industrial production successfully.

(ii) Since an effective industrial use for phenanthrene waste has not been found in China, it was commonly heaped at the site of the manufacturer as the form of a waste, seriously polluting the environment. Thereby, it was important that we employed phenanthrene waste as raw materials and obtained commercial phenanthrene by using a simple method.

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